

THE IMPACT OF CULTURE IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *This article will discuss about the importance of culture while learning or instructing English as a foreign language. The difference between the classes conducted with mixing the particular culture with language and the ones those have only language lessons .By the way , the different ways for how to deal with those problems in accepting the language and culture together during the process.*

Keywords: *culture, phrases, communication, intercultural, language, English, culture consolidation, lessons, second language.*

ВЛИЯНИЕ КУЛЬТУРЫ НА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ И ИЗУЧЕНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В этой статье речь пойдет о важности культуры при изучении или преподавании английского языка как иностранного. Разница между занятиями, проводимыми со смешением определенной культуры с языком, и теми, в которых есть только уроки языка. Кстати, разные способы решения этих проблем при принятии языка и культуры вместе во время процесса.*

Ключевые слова: *культура, фразы, общение, межкультурное, язык, английский язык, консолидация культуры, уроки, второй язык.*

INTRODUCTION

As language considered one part of the culture, both language and culture should be learned widely in order to understand and go deeper in that knowledge. Nowadays ,it is widely obvious that English is accepted as an international language all over the world , so knowing how to use,when to use different pharses and collocations in that language is an indispensable ability. Before starting to learn a second language like English , the realization of acquiring detailed information about that culture the language is connected. Actually, culture includes what people do and what they usually believe. That is the reason why it profoundly effects the imagination of the person learning a second language and determines the methods of teaching and learning too.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to Wei (2005:56), language has a dual character: both as a tool of communication and a carrier of culture. Language without culture is unthinkable, so is human culture without language. .That is the reason why ,culture is usually seen as a mirror of a partucular language.

Educating a new language implies planning your understudies for real-life circumstances they are likely to come across whereas going by any western nation for case in arrange to dodge being confused, humiliated or avoided from communication, or totally misconstrued. The goal of instruction isn't local speaker competence in target language. Or maybe, it is creating intercultural communicative competence in understudies through culture consolidation socially based educating hone interfaces dialect to its characteristic partner i.e. culture, raises boost and creates intercultural competence in learners, empowering them to suitably decipher and get it culturally-induced behaviors. Agreeing to Middle easterner teachers, in any case, learner's

neighborhood culture ought to be given significance in educating of English dialect since off-base interpretation and transliteration of Islamic concepts cause an mental and otherworldly catastrophe of the most elevated magnitude.

Social orders which live in numerous regions of the world have distinctive social childhoods, values, demeanors and foundations and utilize diverse dialects. Language and culture appear on the surface to be two distinctive areas, but they have an entrapped relationship and influence each other commonly. Gleason (1961) demonstrated that dialects are not as it were the items of societies, but moreover are the images of societies. The development of a dialect habitually influences its related culture, and social designs of cognition and custom are often explicitly coded in that language .In addition, language is additionally a social institution, both forming and being shaped by society (Armour-Thomas & Gopaul-McNicol, 1998). This implies that dialect isn't an autonomous develop but social hone both making and being made by the structures and powers of social educate in which we live and work.

RESULTS

In learning approximately culture within the language classroom, we got to draw on our claim experiences of dialect and culture as they are experienced when attempting to make and interpret meanings. The capacity to memorize beyond the classroom is likely more imperative than any particular data that understudies may learn around another culture amid their schooling. This is often since it is outlandish to instruct all of any culture since societies are variable and assorted. As language teachers know that what able to educate within the classroom is definitely as it were a fractional picture of a dialect and culture. By acknowledging that confinement in our possess educating, we are less likely to create stereotypical sees of the societies we are instructing approximately. Learning how to memorize almost culture implies that, as individuals lock in with modern viewpoints of culture, they create their knowledge and mindfulness and discover ways of acting agreeing to their unused learning.

Due to Tomalin (2008), the international role of the English language and globalization are the two main reasons to teach culture as a fifth language skill, in addition to listening, speaking, reading and writing.

DISCUSSION

Understanding the relationship between culture and language will offer assistance us to create guidelines techniques and pedagogies for teaching pupils foreign language like English.. Language could be a part of culture and culture could be a portion of language. The two are unequivocally subordinate on each other and ought to be instructed that way as well. Since inspiration is pivotal for learning a second language .Instructors shuld point to form their dialect instruction as much curiously and relevantly pertinent as conceivable. Culturally-based ELT classrooms prepare learners with intercultural competencies to effectively communicate in today's globalized world. Outside culture and one's possess culture ought to be utilized together in arrange for learners to get it a remote culture.

CONCLUSION

All things considered, the lessons conducted with both mixing culture and language would be the great way to go further and learn every single thing easily and fast rather than the classes only aim to teach the language only .To sum up, instructors ought to let learners not as it were pay consideration to social contrasts but too attempt to get it and study the contrasts to dodge misconception in consider and communication. It is fundamental for understudies to be

taught straightforwardly and create their mindfulness of social foundation information in arrange to overcome the deterrents.

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